

pyCSEP: A Python Toolkit For Earthquake Forecast Developers

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Summary

For government officials and the public to act on real-time forecasts of earthquakes, the seismological community needs to develop confidence in the underlying scientific hypotheses of the forecast generating models by assessing their predictive skill. For this purpose, the Collaboratory for the Study of Earthquake Predictability (CSEP) provides cyberinfrastructure and computational tools to evaluate earthquake forecasts. Here, we introduce pyCSEP, a Python package to help earthquake forecast developers embed model evaluation into the model development process. The package contains the following modules: (1) earthquake catalog access and processing, (2) data models for earthquake forecasts, (3) statistical tests for evaluating earthquake forecasts, and (4) visualization routines. pyCSEP can evaluate earthquake forecasts expressed as expected rates in space-magnitude bins, and simulation-based forecasts that produce thousands of synthetic seismicity catalogs. Most importantly, pyCSEP contains community-endorsed implementations of statistical tests to evaluate earthquake forecasts, and provides well defined file formats and standards to facilitate model comparisons. The toolkit will facilitate integrating new forecasting models into testing centers, which evaluate forecast models and prediction algorithms in an automated, prospective and independent manner, forming a critical step towards reliable operational earthquake forecasting.

Background

Successfully predicting the time, location, and size of future earthquakes would have immense societal value, and this quest underlies much of the research in seismology and earthquake geology. To date, however there have been no reliable earthquake predictions methods. An earthquake prediction is a deterministic statement about whether or not an earthquake will occur in a particular geographic region, time window, and magnitude range. On the other hand, an earthquake forecast provides the probability that such an earthquake will occur ([Jordan et al., 2011](#)). Most of the current research effort focuses on developing probabilistic earthquake forecasting models that encode empirical or physics-based hypotheses about the occurrence of seismicity. To what degree earthquakes can be predicted remains an open and important question.

As [Schorlemmer et al. \(2018\)](#) states “the fundamental idea of CSEP is simple in principle but complex in practice: earthquake forecasts should be tested against future observations to assess their performance, thereby ensuring an unbiased test of the forecasting power of a model.” Practically, this requires a prospective evaluation of the earthquake forecasts. Prospective

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evaluation requires that model developers fully specify their models (with zero-degrees of freedom) before the experiment begins (Schorlemmer et al., 2018). Specific parameters for an experiment are determined through community consensus, such as the geographic testing region and magnitude range, authoritative data sets used to evaluate the forecasts, the evaluation metrics, and the precise specification of a forecast. These parameters are defined in full before the start of the experiment. This standardization ensures that any potential conscious or unconscious biases are reduced, because the evaluation data are collected after each model has been provided for evaluation.

Statement of need

Over the last decade, CSEP has led numerous prospective earthquake forecasting experiments (see, e.g., Michael & Werner, 2018). These experiments are formally conducted within testing centers (Schorlemmer & Gerstenberger, 2007) that contain the software required to autonomously run and evaluate earthquake forecasts in a fully prospective mode. The software design emphasized a carefully controlled computing and software environment which ensured integrity of testing results (Zechar et al., 2009). However, its monolithic software design made it difficult for researchers to utilize various routines in the testing centers in their own work without replicating the entire testing center configuration on their own system. In addition, software was developed by a single developer, leading to personnel risk and a lack of opportunities for others to contribute directly.

pyCSEP was designed to provide vetted methods to evaluate earthquake forecasts in a Python package that researchers can include directly in their research. The statistical tests and tools to evaluate earthquake forecasts are required by all model developers, and greatly benefit from open-source development practices by providing standardized, well-tested, and community-reviewed software tools. At the time of publication, pyCSEP has been used for two published articles (Bayona et al., 2020; Savran et al., 2020), and is being used by several research groups participating in the [Real-time earthquake risk reduction for a resilient Europe \(RISE\)](#) project and others.

pyCSEP Overview

pyCSEP provides an open-source implementation of peer-reviewed statistical tests developed for evaluating probabilistic earthquake forecasts (Rhoades et al., 2011; Savran et al., 2020; Schorlemmer et al., 2007; Werner et al., 2011; Zechar et al., 2013). In addition, pyCSEP provides routines for working with earthquake catalogs and visualizations. The core design of pyCSEP includes classes that represent earthquake forecasts, catalogs, and various spatial regions. Higher level functions are implemented using these classes to provide routines for common tasks in evaluating earthquake forecasts.

Earthquake forecasts can either be specified as expected earthquake rates over discrete space-magnitude-time regions (Schorlemmer et al., 2007) or as families of synthetic earthquake catalogs with each catalog representing a realization from the underlying stochastic model (e.g., Savran et al., 2020). Earthquake catalogs are row-based data sets that contain features of an earthquake. At a minimum, an earthquake must be defined by its geographical location (latitude, longitude), origin time, and magnitude. In addition, pyCSEP provides classes for working directly with forecasts from the Uniform California Earthquake Rupture Forecast with Epidemic-type Aftershock Sequences Version 3 (Field et al., 2017). pyCSEP also provides classes for interacting with earthquake catalogs and performing operations on them, such as filtering and binning events on the space-magnitude grids needed for evaluation. pyCSEP also includes numerous plotting utilities that interface directly with `matplotlib` and `Cartopy` (Hunter, 2007; Met Office, 2010 - 2015). Space-magnitude regions facilitate gridding operations

that are necessary for evaluating earthquake forecasts. These objects model regular latitude, longitude cells where earthquakes can be aggregated for evaluation and visualization purposes. pyCSEP provides pre-defined spatial regions that have been used in previous experiments (Field, 2007; Taroni et al., 2018).

pyCSEP interfaces directly with popular numerical and plotting libraries such as Numpy, matplotlib, and pandas (Harris et al., 2020; Hunter, 2007; McKinney, 2010). Users already familiar with these libraries can adapt pyCSEP directly into their code. pyCSEP provides file-formats for forecasts and earthquake catalogs, and can allow users to specify custom filetypes.

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